

RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING OF COMPLEX TEXTILE COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

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SUMMARY: It has been established that composite parts with considerable geometric complexity and close dimensional tolerances can be fabricated with high fiber volume, low void content and a dependable fiber architecture by using the resin transfer molding (RTM) process. This paper addresses the techniques utilized for obtaining a composite box section with 55-58% fiber volume using eight plies of a 4-harness carbon fabric with a quasi-isotropic stacking sequence. One of the enabling features of the fabrication procedure was using a tackified fabric to shape a preform that fits into the mold cavity. The mold was heated with hot oil. The matrix, 3M's PR-500 Epoxy, was injected into an evacuated mold using a Graco RTM Injector. Test coupons were cut from the composite boxes to determine various mechanical properties. The properties from sides of the box were compared with those from the bottom of the box. The mechanical properties of the corners (through-the-thickness tensile strength) of the box were also determined. The tensile properties from the box compared favorably with the panel data but compression properties did not. The properties of the sides and the bottom of the box compared favorably. The paper contains the details of the composite box fabrication process as well as the determination of its mechanical properties.

KEYWORDS: Resin transfer molding; Composite fabrication and testing; Casket molding techniques; Tackified textile fabrics; Mechanical property evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

The interest in the fabrication of geometrically complex aircraft parts utilizing the resin transfer molding (RTM) processes is increasing. RTM parts are now being used in critical structural components of both commercial and military aircraft. This use is due, in part, to improvements in RTM fabrication methods which allow parts to be produced with greater geometric complexity and closer dimensional tolerances than possible using other (customary) composite manufacturing methods [1]. RTM fabrication also allows parts to be manufactured with fiber volume ratios comparable to those achievable with autoclave processing techniques [2-7]. The objective of the present research was to design, fabricate, analyze and test a high performance RTM composite component. The composite component should incorporate a complex geometric configuration, close dimensional tolerances and a high fiber volume using a high performance matrix and fiber. This paper details the mold design, RTM process and the evaluation of the mechanical properties of an illustrative aircraft part.

TECHNICAL APPROACH

The design of the part was based on an aircraft type spar that might be included in the tail section of an advanced aircraft. The part was sized to be compatible with existing RTM equipment. It contained eight plies of IM7-6k-4HS carbon fiber fabric stacked in quasi-isotropic sequence. It was designed in an open-box configuration about seven inches long and

three inches wide with a uniform wall thickness. The sides were two inches high and were at right angles to the base. The selection of the size was based on an interest in obtaining the tensile-, compression-, and 'L-beam'- test coupons from the same box section. The angle (called here as L-beam) section, subject of an earlier research [8], required two-inch long legs for comparative studies. The eight (fabric) plies were to be consolidated to 0.067 inches of wall thickness to obtain a fiber volume in the range of 55-58%.

The matrix used was 3M company's PR-500 Epoxy Resin. It is an advanced fluorinated epoxy packaged as a one component system especially formulated for RTM [1]. The matrix system is compatible with our Graco Heated RTM Supply Pump. Since the matrix is a thick paste at room temperature, the pumping and plumbing system must be controlled at an elevated temperature. The mold design selected was of the casket- type. This type of mold concept is especially useful for vacuum filling because it only has two matrix ports and one O'ring seal. In addition, the casket components are heated by hot oil which provides for rapid heating and cooling as well as uniform temperature control. The casket design concept is especially useful as it provides an opportunity to reduce the cost of individual composite components by injecting a multi-cavity mold with one injection cycle.

Because of the geometric complexity of the part design, tackified woven fabric was used so that the preform could be fully consolidated into the part configuration before it is placed into the mold cavity. This concept assures the stability of the ply architecture when the sides of the preform are put in shear as the mold closes. The mold was held in a compression press during the RTM process because the liquid matrix was to be held at 150 psi during the fabrication process. The press platens keep the mold closed and minimize the deflection of the mold components at this hydraulic pressure as well as affect a vacuum- and fluid- seal.

MATERIALS

Matrix: The matrix chosen for this project was PR-500 Epoxy Resin produced and marketed by the 3M Company [2]. It is a proprietary one-component fluorinated epoxy resin especially formulated for the fabrication of advanced composites by the RTM process. It is a high strength epoxy with exceptionally good mechanical properties, especially under wet conditions. The Graco Heated RTM Supply Pump [8] was designed for injecting the matrix material into an RTM mold. The matrix contains a powdered catalyst suspended in the thick epoxy matrix paste. The catalyst melts at approximately 280⁰ F. The latent catalyst must be melted before it reaches the fiber preform., otherwise the preform would filter the powdered catalyst out of the matrix before it dissolves in the epoxy. This feature was particularly useful for the RTM process because it allowed the matrix to be pumped through the plumbing before the matrix was activated by dissolving the powdered catalyst. Therefore, the plumbing between the pump and the mold was almost all reusable between injection cycles without cleaning.

Reinforcement: The reinforcement chosen was IM7-6k-4HS provided by Dow-UT. It was a 4-harness fabric woven from 6k-IM7 carbon fibers with a tackifying agent added to one surface. Dow-UT distributes and fuses a powdered version of PR-500, labeled as PT-500, to the fabric as a tackifying agent. The tackifying agent allows for the construction of a preform out of a stack of fabric plies to fit a mold cavity with complex geometry. The tackified material melts during the preform molding and resolidifies upon cooling. The preform not only was shaped but also consolidated to the part thickness to minimize the stress on the preform during mold closing.

FABRICATION PROCESS

Mold: The following illustration, Fig. 1, is useful in describing the primary features of the casket mold design. The casket cavity and casket top plate are designed to contain hot oil channels for heating and cooling the mold. Inside the casket cavity was the cavity insert. This insert contains the mold cavity which forms the outside surface of the composite part. Attached to the casket top plate was the cavity punch. One of the surfaces of the punch

formed the inside surface of the composite part. The cavity insert also contained the matrix manifold. The matrix manifold distributed the matrix along the long edge of the part. The matrix entered the casket cavity along one edge of the part and overflowed on the other edge as it exited the mold cavity. An O-ring seal was used to form the required vacuum seal between the casket top plate and the casket cavity. The carbon fiber preform fits into the mold cavity as shown. The entire assembly was clamped by a compression press. The fit between the casket cavity and the cavity insert was a slip fit. The space shown between the mold components in Fig. 1 is for the purpose of illustration only. The illustration also exaggerates the taper between the cavity insert and the casket cavity. The mold was machined from tool steel to close tolerances and with a good machine finish on important surfaces.

Fig. 1: Casket Mold for RTM

The Graco Heated RTM Supply Pump: The Graco Heated RTM Supply Pump [3] was designed to inject a single component matrix with a high room-temperature viscosity. The machine was designed to utilize the matrix shipping container as the matrix supply vessel. A can opener was used to convert the shipping container to matrix supply vessel by cutting off the friction fastener ledge. The temperature controlled Wiper Plate Assembly was pressed into the top of the can by the two air cylinders and allowed to rest on the top of the matrix surface as shown in Fig. 2. The heat from the Wiper Plate Assembly reduces the viscosity of the matrix so that it may be pumped into the mold. The matrix was pumped with an air powered reciprocating piston pump. Each stroke of the pump delivers 6 ml of matrix. A needle valve in the plumbing system regulates the matrix flow rate. The flow rate selected for this part was 6 ml per minute. It is imperative that the temperature of the plumbing be carefully controlled. If it is too cold, the matrix will not flow, and if it is too hot, the matrix will set-up in the plumbing thereby stopping the flow and damaging the plumbing for future use. For PR-500, the in-let plumbing temperature was set at 150⁰ F. The out-let plumbing temperature was set 200⁰ F. As the matrix is pumped out of the container, the air cylinders keep a constant pressure on the matrix hot plate to maintain its contact with the surface of the matrix in the supply container. In addition, the system only heats the matrix in contact with the heated hot plate. It minimizes the heat history of the matrix not immediately required.

Plumbing System: The plumbing system is illustrated in Fig. 3. The mold was placed in the compression press and the copper tubing was assembled as shown. Copper tubing, 1/4 inch outer diameter with 37 degree flared tube fittings, was used throughout. At the time of assembly a small amount of vacuum grease was applied to each joint to enhance the vacuum seal. All of the plumbing on the matrix entrance side of the mold was wrapped with electrical heating tape and adjusted to 150⁰ F. The plumbing temperature on the matrix exit side of the mold was set at 200⁰ F. The exit side of the mold contained a shut-off valve, a matrix trap,

vacuum gage and a vacuum pump. The entrance side of the mold contained a shut-off valve, a needle valve and the Graco Heated RTM Supply Pump.

Fig. 2: Graco Heated RTM Supply Pump

Fig. 3: Injection Set-up Showing Plumbing Arrangement

The plumbing was vacuum tested to determine if the system was vacuum tight. This was accomplished by closing the inlet valve, opening the outlet valve and turning on the vacuum pump. After the vacuum reached about 30 inches of Mercury, the vacuum pump was turned off and the vacuum gage was observed for vacuum leaks. If the gage indicated a leak of over one inch in 15 minutes, all of the plumbing connections were retightened and retested. A vacuum tight plumbing system is required for a successful RTM molding cycle.

Fabrication: The preform was constructed of eight plies of IM7-6k-4HS tackified carbon fiber fabric stacked in a quasi-isotropic sequence. A template was developed which provided a preform that exactly fit the mold cavity. The template was positioned on the fabric in various positions to obtain fiber orientations of +45, -45, 90 and 0 degrees. The plies were then stacked in a sequence of $[+45/0/-45/90]_s$. The stack was placed on the preform molding tool and vacuum bagged as illustrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Tool for Molding Preform

The preform tool was fitted with a thermocouple for temperature measurement. The vacuum bagged preform was placed in an oven preheated to 220⁰ F and the vacuum was then applied to the bag. As the vacuum level increased, the plies of fabric were pulled tight against the preform tool. When the tool reached the oven temperature, it was held for 20 minutes. At this point, the resin had melted. The tool was cooled down to room temperature before the vacuum is released. The result is a molded preform having the shape of the tool and compressed to the approximate consolidation thickness. The preform at this stage can be handled, inspected, and the edges trimmed to precise dimensions. The box design included partially opened corners. The open corners were obtained by trimming the preform about 1/8 inch from each corner. This minimized the problem of trying to mold corners in the box which was unnecessary for the intended box design.

Matrix Injection: The set-up and conditions illustrated in Fig. 3 are used to inject the matrix. A coat of mold release was applied to all surfaces of the mold. The O'ring and O'ring groove were cleaned, lubricated with vacuum grease, and assembled. The preform was placed on the punch and pressed into the mold cavity with the compression press. The equipment arrangement (without the plumbing and the hot oil heating lines) is illustrated in Fig. 5. The vacuum pump, heat to matrix plumbing, heat to Graco wiper plate assembly and heat to the

mold were turned on and allowed to stabilize. Thermocouples were attached to various locations in the matrix plumbing- and mold- equipment. The mold temperature was set at 350⁰ F, the matrix in-let plumbing and Graco wiper plate assembly temperatures were set at 150⁰ F and the matrix out-let plumbing was set at 200⁰ F.

Fig. 5: Equipment Set-up

Before commencing the matrix injection, the vacuum seal was rechecked to determine if the plumbing joints continued to seal at elevated temperature. If a leak was found, it was repaired and rechecked. The compressed air to the Graco was adjusted to 40 psi with the needle valve closed. The air to the air cylinders was set at 10 psi and the air to the matrix pump was set at 22 psi. The vacuum pump was turned off. The needle valve was slowly opened and the frequency of the pump stroke was observed and the needle valve adjusted to provide one stroke per minute. When the matrix was observed to flow into the matrix trap, the matrix exit valve was closed and the matrix pump increased the liquid matrix pressure to 150 psi. The exit valve was opened briefly two times to “burp” a small amount of matrix through the mold. Finally, the matrix was pressurized to 150 psi and held for 30 minutes.. The referenced literature indicated that the matrix would gel in 30 minutes at 350⁰ F. This pressurization reduced the size of any remaining air voids and matrix polymerization shrinkage.

Cure and Part Removal: The mold was held at 350⁰ F for two hours as recommend by the matrix manufacturer to achieve a full cure. The removal of the part from the mold caused some initial difficulty. After a number of attempts, the following part ejection technique was determined. Four undercut slots, 0.25” wide x 2.0” long x 0.030” deep, were added to the cavity punch. These under cuts aided removal of the part from the cavity insert by having the part remain on the punch as the mold halves were separated. The mold halves were separated at the cure temperature of 350⁰ F and the part was removed from the punch after the punch

reached room temperature. This sequence was necessary because the part had a lower thermal coefficient of expansion than the mold steel.

MECHANICAL TESTING

The mechanical properties of the molded box were determined by extracting test coupons from both the bottom and sides of the box. The data determined for the bottom and side coupons were kept separate in order to compare the properties of the composite materials from the two locations. A difference in properties may occur because the sides of the preform are in shear and compression as the mold closes while the bottom is only in compression. The mechanical test selected are: tensile, compression and L-beam. Standard ASTM test procedures were used in testing the specimens. The L-beam test method was described in detail by Avva et. al. [8]. This test method measures the “through-the-thickness” tensile strength which is useful for designing structures subjected to out-of-plane loads.

Test Coupon Dimensions: The procedures for the compression and tensile testing follow the ASTM D 3410 and ASTM D 3039 standards, respectively. The test coupon size was scaled down to fit the size limitations that resulted from the composite box. For example, normally the standard ASTM tension coupons are cut from panels with 0.100-inch thick, but the box in the present case was only 0.067-inch thick. The scaling resulted in coupons that were approximately 67% of the ASTM’s standard size. The L-beam specimen includes material taken from the side, corner and bottom of the box section. The L-beam coupons tested here are also scaled-down versions of geometry and dimensions as shown in [8].

Tensile Data - Box Bottom

<u>Box/Number</u>	<u>Failure Strength</u>	<u>Axial Strain</u>	<u>Modulus</u>	<u>Poisson’s Ratio</u>
5/21	99.8 ksi	1.31 %	7.6 Msi	.32
5/30	102.8	1.40	7.6	.33
6/18	97.4	1.30	7.5	.34
6/25	92.7	1.20	7.6	---
7/30	95.4	1.30	7.3	.30
8/19	107.7	1.27	8.2	.30
8/26	98.0	1.30	7.7	.33
9/30	106.3	1.34	8.0	.38
Average	100.0/689(ksi/MPa)	1.30 %	7.7/53(Msi/GPa)	.33

Tensile Data - Box Side

<u>Box/Number</u>	<u>Failure Strength</u>	<u>Axial Strain</u>	<u>Modulus</u>	<u>Poisson’s Ratio</u>
5/21	95.5 ksi	1.30 %	7.3 Msi	.32
5/30	100.7	1.30	7.8	.33
6/18	102.1	1.38	7.4	.31
6/25	93.6	1.21	7.7	.34
7/30	91.5	1.20	7.6	.31
8/19	100.1	1.32	7.6	.31
8/26	91.3	1.30	7.2	.34
9/30	107.3	1.34	8.1	.39
Average	97.8/674 (ksi/MPa)	1.29 %	7.6/52 (Msi/GPa)	.33

Compression Data - Box Bottom

<u>Box/Number</u>	<u>Failure Strength</u>	<u>Axial Strain</u>	<u>Modulus</u>	<u>Poisson's Ratio</u>
5/21	60.7 ksi	1.20 %	5.5 Msi	.30
5/30	56.6	0.81	6.9	.30
6/18	57.7	1.00	5.6	.31
6/25	70.6	1.06	6.5	.32
8/19	71.5	0.71	7.6	.36
9/30	67.9	0.70	8.4	.40
Average	64.2/443(ksi/MPa)	0.91 %	6.8/46.9 (Msi/GPa)	.33

Compression Data - Box Side

<u>Box/Number</u>	<u>Failure Strength</u>	<u>Axial Strain</u>	<u>Modulus</u>	<u>Poisson's Ratio</u>
5/21	54.9 ksi	0.88 %	6.3 Msi	.36
5/30	62.4	0.98	6.3	.32
6/18	68.6	1.06	6.6	.35
6/25	57.4	0.90	6.5	.31
8/19	69.8	0.80	7.9	.40
9/30	66.2	0.70	8.5	.40
Average	63.2/436(ksi/MPa)	0.89 %	7.0/48.2 (Msi/GPa)	.36

Fiber Volume

<u>Box/Number</u> <u>Gravity</u>	<u>Fiber Volume</u>	<u>Specific</u>
5/21	54.7 %	1.53
5/30	54.7	1.53
6/18	49.4	1.51
6/25	52.6	1.52
7/30	55.2	1.57
8/19	53.7	1.60
8/26	61.8	1.60
9/30	58.1	1.62
Average	55.0 %	1.56

L-Beam Data

<u>Box/Number</u>	<u>Failure Strength, ksi</u>
8/26- 1	1.18
2	1.75
3	1.89
Average	1.61/11.1 (ksi/MPa)

ANALYSIS OF DATA

One concern of the fabrication process was the possibility of observing differences in the mechanical properties obtained in testing coupons extracted from the bottom and sides of the molded composite box. In this case, a significant variation of mechanical property data obtained from the referenced two locations was not indicated. One may therefore conclude that the fiber architecture of the side panels was not disturbed by the shear of the preform as the mold was closed.

The only published data for property comparison located in the literature was in the 3M Company's PR-500 Product Bulletin [2]. The 3M data for tensile properties on IM7-6k-4HS in a quasi-isotropic lay-up were on coupons that were 0.100 inches thick and a 58% fiber volume. For this condition, the data reported for the tensile strength was 110 ksi and the tensile modulus was 8.0 Msi. When the tensile data for the box bottom was normalized to a 58% fiber volume, the tensile strength was 105.5 ksi and the tensile modulus was 8.1 Msi. These results compare favorably.

The compression properties do not compare as well as the tensile properties described above. The 3M data for compression strength was 87 ksi and the compression modulus was 7.7 Msi. When the data for the box bottom compression strength was normalized to a 58% fiber volume, the compression strength was 67.7 ksi and compression modulus was 7.1 Msi. Compression testing is a complex arena. It is felt that the scaling from a coupon thickness of 0.100 inches to a thickness of 0.067 may not be logical and could be a source for obtaining property variation. This issue need to be addressed further at a later time.

The L-beam data also proved to be a problem to verify. Through-the-thickness tensile strength [8] for laminated and 3D braided composites were much higher than the present material. A possible explanation could be the difference between the thickness of the test coupons. The data reported in [8] was 2 to 3 times greater than that determined from the coupons taken from current RTM part. To further explain the lower strength values, it is suggested that additional studies be conducted to assess the effect of 'scaling down or up' of the 'standard' specimen dimensions.

CONCLUSIONS

This research was successful in producing a quality aircraft type composite component by the RTM process using the state-of-the-art materials and processes. Test coupons removed from the molded parts were tested for tensile, compressive and through-the-thickness properties. The tensile properties agreed very well with published data, but, unfortunately, the compressive and through-the-thickness data was below the expectations. Scaling down the dimensions of the test coupons was believed to be a problem, however, additional work would be required to verify this belief.

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REFERENCES

1. Gerald J. Sundsrud, "Advantages of a One-part Resin System for Processing Aero-space Parts by Resin Transfer Molding (RTM)" was presented at the *Composites in Manufacturing Conference (SME), Pasadena, CA, January 19, 1993*
2. Product Bulletin, 3M PR-500 Epoxy Resin, Issue No. 3, February 1, 1994
3. Instructions-Parts List, Heated RTM Supply Pump, Graco Inc., Revision D, 1991
4. S. Senibi, E. C. Klang, R. L. Sadler and V. S. Avva, "Resin Transfer Molding (RTM): Experiments with Vacuum Assisted Methods", *Presented at Ninth International Conference on Composite Materials, July 12-16, 1993, Madrid, Spain.*
5. R. L. Sadler, V.S. Avva, S.D. Senibi and E. C. Klang, "Experiments Related to the Fabrication of Graphite/Epoxy Tubes by the Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) Process", *Conference on Flow Processes in Composite Materials '94, University of Galway, July 7-9, 1994, Galway, Ireland.*
6. R. L. Sadler, V. S. Avva, S. D. Senibi and E. C. Klang, "Development of a Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) Process for Fabricating a Seamless Composite Tube" was *Presented at the 26th International SAMPE Technical Conference, October 24-27, 1994, Atlanta, GA.*
7. R. L. Sadler, B. D. Morgan, V. S. Avva and D. J. McPherson Sr., "Resin Transfer Molding of 3-D Braided Through-The-Thickness® Pan-Based Carbon Fiber Preforms with a Cyanate Ester" was *presented at the 1995 JANNAF Interagency Propulsion Subcommittee Joint Meetings, December 4-7, 1995, at Tampa, FL.*
8. V. S. Avva, H. G. Allen and K. N. Shivakumar, "Through-the-Thickness Tension Strength of 3-D Braided Composites", *Journal of Composite Materials, Pages 51-68, Vol. 30, No1/1996.*